

FARG’ONA VODIYSI IQLIMINI GEOEKOLOGIK MUAMMOLARI VA ULARNING YECHIMIGA OID KONTSEPTSIYALAR

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada Farg’ona vodiysida olib borilgan iqlimiy tadqiqotlarda ilgari surilgan kontseptsiyalar va va iqlim bilan bog’liq ekologik muammolar haqida fikrlar yutirilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: Ekologik vaziyat, chiqindilar, tog’ shamollari. atmosfera havosi, meteorologik sharoit, defleatsiya jarayoni.

Abstract. This article presents the concepts and ideas put forward in the climatic studies conducted in the Fergana Valley and the ecological problems associated with the climate.

Keywords: Ecological situation, waste, mountain winds. atmospheric air, meteorological conditions, deflation process.

Introduction: The change in the natural environment and the worsening of the ecological situation in the Fergana Valley are associated with its geographical location, specific natural conditions and factors, existing territorial and local natural laws and regulations, the stability and variability of natural complexes, the nature of the economic activity of the population, the characteristics of the development of production, etc.

The fact that the Fergana Valley is surrounded by high mountain ranges and only in the west it connects with the Tashkent-Mirzachol foothill plain through a narrow corridor (Khujand Gate) and only the Syrdarya flows out of it determines many of its specific individual, local features. In this regard, in particular, the flow of numerous streams from the mountain slopes causes the accumulation of natural and man-made substances in their conical slopes. As groundwater flows through the near-surface layers of the slopes, it dissolves various substances and is saturated with salts, heavy metal ions, petroleum products, pesticides, mineral fertilizers, detergents, industrial waste, etc. Consequently, the cone-shaped depressions are a place of accumulation not only of salts, but also of technogenic waste, some of which is transported by underground flow to the alluvial-proluvial plain - Central Fergana. Therefore, the water of the Syrdarya River is completely unsuitable for drinking, starting from Uchkurgan [1].

Relevance of the research topic: The presence of mountain winds is characteristic of the Fergana Valley. In the north, northern, in the south - southern, in the west - eastern winds. The "Kokand" and "Bekabad" winds are seasonal, sometimes blowing at a speed of 15-20 m per second.

The abundance of mineral resources in the region serves as the basis for the development of industrial production, but due to the specific characteristics of the lowland, technogenic wastes lead to their accumulation in this place. The development of various industrial production and transport leads to the saturation of the environment with technogenic wastes.

The existing industrial enterprises in Khujand, Kokand, Margilan, Fergana, Oltiariq, Kuva, Haydarkon, Sulukta, Kyzylqiya, Qadamjoy, Chauvay, Osh, Jalalabad, Asaka, Andijan,

Namangan and other places surround the valley in a regional manner and pollute it with various wastes. Due to the complexity of their disposal, wastes accumulate in the region, aggravating the ecological situation.

It is worth noting that atmospheric air pollution is caused not only by natural factors, such as dust, but also by the extremely large anthropogenic impact. In the Kirguli industrial zone, the air contains 2.2 times more phenol, 14 times more hydrogen sulfide, and 14 times more hydrocarbons.

No one denies that the aggravation of the ecological situation in the city of Kuvasoy and its environs in the 80s-90s of the last century was associated with the activities of a cement production enterprise located in the region. Fourth, an average of 743 tons of cement dust, 33 tons of lime dust, 542 tons of organic and inorganic dusts are emitted per km² per year (Sultonov, 1995). If we take into account the dust, toxic gases and waste emitted by the cement plant, paint factories, "Quartz" and reinforced concrete associations, GRES and other production enterprises, as well as vehicles, in addition to the city, the ecological situation becomes even more serious.

Due to the peculiarities of meteorological conditions in the Fergana Valley, namely, the stagnation of the air, especially in summer, the dispersion of waste in it is slowed down, which can be clearly felt in residential areas. In the Kirguli industrial zone of Fergana, bitter smog occurs in autumn and winter, which indicates the stagnation of atmospheric air at certain times and confirms its pollution. It has been found that air pollution increases from west to east and from north to south [2].

Purpose and objectives: Analysis of the dynamics of atmospheric air pollution in the cities of the Fergana Valley according to the data of the State Committee for Nature Protection of the Republic (1998,1999, 2000, 2010, 2020) made it possible to determine the following results.

First of all, we can see that by 2019, compared to 1990, the amount of emissions into the atmosphere has decreased by 2 times. However, in the cities of Fergana, Kokand, Andijan and neighboring republics, atmospheric air pollution still remains at a high level.

It can be seen that in 1990, the amount of waste in the cities of Uzbekistan alone was 151.3 thousand tons, while the total amount of waste in the same cities by 2020 amounted to 64.0 thousand tons. This is in any case a satisfactory level.

The Fergana Valley is a typical area where deflation and erosion processes occur on a large scale. Precipitation in the form of floods, hail, and torrential rains prevail in the low mountains and hills. Expert opinions on this have been published. Erosion is particularly developed in the Namangan, Osh, and Fergana regions. Only 60-65% of the hilly lands of the Namangan region have been eroded (Qazokov, 2015). During the leaching of fertile humus layers of soils, their amount has decreased to 30-45%, and their mechanical composition has become coarse. Consequently, the leaching of the humus layer negatively affects the normal vegetation of plants [3].

Results and discussion: Remote sensing is of great importance in detecting, monitoring and inferring climate change. The main advantages of remote sensing are the high speed of obtaining data on large volumes of the atmosphere or large areas of the earth's surface, as well as obtaining information that is not available with other research methods. For the purpose of traditional metrological measurements of the upper atmosphere, extensive and complex systematic methods of remote sensing using balloon probes are used.

Forecasting and early warning systems for irrigation water supply are crucial for the well-planned planting of agricultural crops. In this regard, the project envisages providing agrometeorological information services to communities engaged in the cultivation of fruit and vegetable crops in the Fergana Valley. They will be provided with improved observational forecasting data and relevant advisory services on the cultivation of climate-resilient fruit and vegetable crops. They will also gain knowledge about the impact of climate change on planning fruit and vegetable production.

Such measures aimed at supporting private producers are important and necessary for the recovery of private fruit and vegetable businesses in the post-coronavirus pandemic period, as well as for protecting them from climate risks. The project will also have a positive impact on communities in neighboring countries living in the Fergana Valley by strengthening regional cooperation in the exchange of hydrometeorological information obtained as a result of observations in transboundary areas [4].

Conclusion: Climate change processes observed in Uzbekistan since 1951 have been twice as high as the global average and have demonstrated the presence of large-scale climate hazards. A particularly difficult situation has arisen in the Aral Sea region and the eastern part of the Fergana Valley, where drought, desertification and extreme seasonal weather events are becoming more complicated by climate change and threaten the basic well-being and food security of the local population. Therefore, it is necessary to urgently implement scientifically based adaptation measures in the agricultural sector in order to prevent a decrease in productivity and agricultural productivity, and to provide the most vulnerable groups with the means of livelihood and food. Based on the above considerations and considerations, we have developed a periodicity of climatic changes and geocological problems in the Fergana Valley. By studying this periodicity, it is possible to analyze the dynamics of geocological problems formed in the region.

The geocological problems that have arisen in the Fergana Valley and the concepts (views, ideas) related to their solution have also been developed by us, through which a system of measures to improve the state of the environment in the region can be developed[5].

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